

**ANTHROPOGENIC LANDSCAPES AND PROSPECTS OF ECOTOURISM
IN THE AREA OF THE BURGUNDY RESERVOIR.**

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Abstract: The article gives an idea that anthropogenic landscapes are specific geotechnical or natural-territorial complexes, in their use, along with the study of the formation, development, changes in them, of course, it is important to stratify, classify anthropogenic landscapes.

Keywords: ecotourism, anthropogenic landscape, recreation resources, trinity, mineralogical, bacteriological.

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1. Introduction.

Anthropogen landscapes are considered as specific geotechnical or natural-territorial complexes, in their use anthropogen landscapes are formed, developed, along with the study of changes in them, of course it is important to stratify, classify anthropogen landscapes. In the classification of Anthropoid landscapes, the separation of its morphological units is the main factor[1]. Because in the stratification of anthropogen landscapes into taxonomic units of different categories, the pre-landscape phase is divided into zonal, azonal, regional and height based on the regionalization.

And the anthropogen landscape structure, along with the observance of the commonality rule, which is subject to all the above laws, also namesakes specific private aspects. Accordingly, the separation and study of its morphological units within the framework of the Anthropoid landscape is of great importance today in the development of ecotourism in all systems of the national economy and especially in the environment of water reservoirs, in the use of recreational and recreational resources, in agriculture, as well as in the study of such cases, the relevance Today, as is the case in all spheres of our country's life, extensive reforms such as the development of ecotourism, recreation, the use of Reclamation resources are deeply entering.

2. The purpose of the research:

The territory of the Tudakul water reservoir is administratively completely isolated; only the south-west border of the territory of the Navoi region belonging

to the Kiziltepa district is around the Buxoro region's Kızıltepa water distribution, that is, the corridor from this water distribution to the Khojrab water distribution from the khojrab lowland. From the point of view of natural geography, the territory is located within the lower Zarafshan district, in other words Zarafshan occupies the south-eastern edge of the natural geographic District [3].

From an economic and social point of view, this territory is very important for the Bukhara-Navoi regions. Because irrigation farming, drinking water sources are considered as well as dumpers, dumping reservoirs and associated hydrotechnical structures: a part of Amu-Buxoro machine channel, dumpers "Trinity", "Kuyimozor", "Kızıltepa", "Navoi" pumps are located in this area. The area has a slightly oblique rectangular shape. It is surrounded by the AMU-Buxoro machine channel by the south-west. Border Hojrab shurkhoghi-expori goes to the border of Buxoro oasis along the southwest skirt of Vali Hill. On the north-west side, however, the border is sharply expressed, surrounded by the Bukhara Oasis, on the north-east side, the border is conditionally crossed by the Khorkhur network of the AMU-Bukhoro machine channel and the middle Channel Uzani. Here the mountains of Karatogh (669, 741 m) of the Ziyovuddin mountains surround the territory as a natural wall. From the south-eastern side, the territory is surrounded by the Buermana mountains (297, 334, 347 m) plateau. And from the south side is Podautau, adjacent to the Uchkum Plains (the width of the "Trinity"-The Well of Shahimardon). The average depth of the elk levels 222 meters is about 300 m.[5]

Picture-1. General view of the water of the duckling.

More than seventy percent of the territory of Uzbekistan belongs to the arid-steppe zone, that is, to the steppe and foothills, to the steppe-dry steppe zone. Oasis built in this zone, economic and social systems and water supply of the population are satisfied mainly from the account of Water Resources coming from other regions. Therefore, the problem of drinking and irrigation water in our republic today is one of the tasks at the level of state policy.

For this reason, it is necessary to engage in work, taking into account the idea of linking resources with each other in the use of Natural Resources in the anthropogenic landscapes in the zone of the Swarm reservoir or in their evaluation. Especially due to the influence of climate change and other anthropogenic factors, the glaciers formed today in Amudarya, Sirdarya, Zarafshan rivers are reduced by an average of 30 percent and the water level of the rivers is sharply reduced. Due to the desertification taking place in the steppe zone, summers are increasingly sensitive to biodiversity and reduction of the gene pool, salinity of soils, swamps, and mineralogical, bacteriological pollution.

One of the strategic ways to solve the water problem in the Republic of Uzbekistan, mitigate it, is the effective use of waters formed due to atmospheric precipitation in the desert zone (landscapes), as well as the organization of ecotourism in the surrounding regions[4].

Picture-2. Sources of saturation of rivers.

Although less visible than one, in fact, due to atmospheric precipitation, a large amount of water is formed in the steppe zone. According to our calculations, the average annual amount of atmospheric precipitation in the territory of Bukhara region is 130 mm, and 1m³ of water is formed on every 7,7 m² area. The average annual gross volume of atmospheric precipitation is 5,2 km³. It is more than five times the capacity of the dump Reservoir (1 km³) or more than the annual flow (4,3-4,8 km³) of the Amu-Buxoro machine channel (partly supplying the Navoi region with water) [4]. Our ancestors came from such waters effectively over the past centuries. To collect and spend water, they built various hydro technical structures. Those who effectively use steppe slopes on the basis of great experience. In the following centuries, the use of local water resources, formed in the steppe

zone, remained unnoticed. The development of methods of enrichment of springs using atmospheric precipitation is one of the most urgent tasks of today. And the hydro technical structures created by our ancestors are now preserved in some places as historical monuments. It is desirable to organize Eco touristic zones around these ancient historical monuments. Today, countries that initially understood the important role of ecotourism in the protection of nature and the formation of ecological consciousness and culture in humans, adopted the recorded methods and international models without any hesitation and developed ecotourism in their own countries. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "on measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated December 2, 2016 № PF-4861 created a radical turn in the development of tourism in our country, the ground of a new stage, the conditions for future reforms. In the presidential decree:

"In the rapid development of tourism in the country, in the more complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism potential:

development and implementation of national and regional programmers of internal and external tourism development";

Development of objects of the tourism industry in all regions of the Republic that meet the requirements and needs of modern world standards, tourists; established.

The decree is aimed at ensuring the rapid development of the tourism network, giving tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, turning it into a powerful tool for sustainable development of the country's economy, effective use of tourism potential in the regions, strengthening the role of tourism in increasing the standard and quality of life of the population. This decree serves as the main program for the smooth development of all types of tourism in our country, regional and regional development of Tourism. From this point of view, and the fact that the development of ecotourism in the "decree" is also emphasized, it is time for us to identify serious problems of rapid development of ecotourism and begin scientific and practical research on the development of solutions to these problems. Many problems in the development of ecotourism have also been identified in our country since the introduction of ecotourism.

3. Conclusion:

So far, in the development of ecotourism in our republic, problems with serious solutions are also emerging. The first thing that these problems face is waiting for their solution, the training of qualified personnel for ecotourism. The relevance of the development of ecotourism-recreation routes to these reserves in the use of State nature reserves in the development of ecotourism in our country consists of the above-mentioned bases. About the essence and content of

ecotourism "International Union of Nature Protection", "International Society of Tourism", "universal fund of wildlife" and many other international organizations adopted the definition of ecotourism of the whole world Tourism Organization [5]. As can be seen from the definitions above about the object and subject of ecotourism, ecological tourism has gradually entered the world tourism industry since the end of the last century. To date, ecotourism has become one of the spheres of the economy, which is rapidly developing in the world. So, in place of the conclusion, it should be noted that the theoretical and practical issues of environmental tourism in our country have been studied in different directions and in different directions. This is evidenced by the fact that the opportunities for the development of this direction in our country are quite sufficient. Especially noteworthy in this regard is the eternity of opportunities in the territory of the Burgundy reservoir.

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